

MIKROORGANIZMLARNING EKZOPOLISAXARIDLAR SINTEZ QILISH QOBILIYATIGA Cr(VI) IONLARINING TA'SIRI

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Annotatsiya. Ekzopolisaxaridlar (EPS) sintezi bakteriyalarning og'ir metallar bilan ifloslangan muhitga moslashishida muhim himoya mexanizmlaridan biri hisoblanadi. Ushbu tadqiqotda *Bacillus* va *Pseudomonas* avlodlariga mansub bakteriya shtammlarining EPS sintez qilish faolligi Cr⁶⁺ ionlari ta'sirida yuzaga keladigan stress sharoitida o'rganildi. Olingan natijalarga ko'ra, *Bacillus licheniformis* 10 va *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* 18 shtamlari Cr⁶⁺ ning 112,04 mg/l va 224,08 mg/l kontsentrasiyalarida o'sishning 7 kuni davomida mos ravishda 177 mg/l va 136 mg/l hamda 147 mg/l va 102 mg/l EPS sintez qilishi kuzatildi. Xususan, o'stirishning 7 kuni Cr(VI) ning 112,04 mg/l kontsentrasiyasida *Bacillus licheniformis* 10 va *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* 18 kulturasining EPS sintez qilish faolligi nazorat variantiga nisbatan 58,7% va 51,7% ga ko'p bo'lishi taxlil etildi.

Kalit so'zlar: og'ir metallar, xrom, ekzopolisaxaridlar, bioremediatsiya, chidamlilik

Аннотация. Синтез экзополисахаридов (ЭПС) является одним из важных защитных механизмов адаптации бактерий к среде, загрязненной тяжелыми металлами. В данной работе изучалась активность синтеза ЭПС штаммов бактерий, принадлежащих к родам *Bacillus* и *Pseudomonas*, в условиях стресса, вызванного действием ионов Cr⁶⁺. Согласно полученным результатам, штаммы *Bacillus licheniformis* 10 и *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* 18 синтезировали 177 мг/л и 136 мг/л и 147 мг/л и 102 мг/л ЭПС в течение 7 суток роста при концентрации Cr⁶⁺ 112,04 мг/л и 224,08 мг/л, соответственно. В частности, проанализировано, что активность синтеза ЭПС культур *Bacillus licheniformis* 10 и *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* 18 при концентрации 112,04 мг/л Cr(VI) через 7 суток культивирования была на 58,7% и 51,7% выше контрольного варианта.

Ключевые слова: тяжелые металлы, хром, экзополисахариды, биоремедиация, устойчивость

Annotation. Synthesis of exopolysaccharides (EPS) is one of the important protective mechanisms of bacterial adaptation to the environment contaminated with heavy metals. In this work, the EPS synthesis activity of bacterial strains belonging to the genera *Bacillus* and *Pseudomonas* was studied under stress conditions caused by the action of Cr⁶⁺ ions. According to the obtained results, the strains *Bacillus licheniformis* 10 and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* 18 synthesized 177 mg/L and 136 mg/L and 147 mg/L and 102 mg/L EPS during 7 days of growth at a Cr⁶⁺ concentration of 112.04 mg/L and 224.08 mg/L, respectively. In particular, it was analyzed that the activity of EPS synthesis on the 7th day of cultivation by the culture of *Bacillus licheniformis* 10 and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* 18 at a Cr(VI) concentration of 112.04 mg/l was 58.7% and 51.7% higher than in the control variant.

Keywords: heavy metals, chromium, exopolysaccharides, bioremediation, resistance

Kirish

Olti valentli xrom (Cr^{6+}) sanoat oqava suvlari va ifloslangan ekotizimlarda mavjud bo'lgan xromning eng zaharli va biologik mavjud shakllaridan biri bo'lib qolmoqda. Yuqori oksidlanish faolligi va eruvchanligi bilan Cr^{6+} hujayra funksiyalarini, metabolizmini va hujayra tuzilmalarining yaxlitligini buzadigan keng ko'lamli biotoksik ta'sirlarni keltirib chiqarishi mumkin [1,2]. Biroq, mikroorganizmlar turli xil himoya mexanizmlari yordamida yuqori Cr^{6+} kontsentratsiyasi bo'lgan sharoitlarga moslashish qobiliyatini namoyon qiladi. Bunday mexanizmlardan biri Cr^{6+} ionlarini adsorbsiyalash, kamaytirish yoki blokirovka qilish, ularni olib tashlash yoki detoksifikatsiya qilishni osonlashtiradigan ekzopolisaxaridlar (EPS) sintezining kuchayishi hisoblanadi. So'nggi tadqiqotlar bu hodisani tasdiqlaydi va mexanizmlar haqidagi tushunchamizni chuqurlashtiradi: Cr^{6+} (12,5-100 mg/l) ta'sirida *Bacillus haynesii* EPS komponentlari (oqsillar 94-119% va polisaxaridlar 2-33% ga) sintezini oshiradi, bu esa Cr^{6+} ning 27,7% ga kamayishiga va EPSda 15,9% gacha saqlanishiga yordam beradi [3]. Cr^{6+} stress ostida *Oceanobacillus oncorhynchi* W4 (galofil bakteriya) maksimal EPS hosildorligi (314,5 mg/L gacha) uchun sharoitlarni optimallashtirishni (pH, saxaroza, inkubatsiya vaqti) namoyish etadi, shu bilan birga Cr^{6+} ni 4 soatdan 5 soatgacha olib tashlashga erishadi. Siyanobakteriyalarda (*Nostoc muscorum*, *Anabaena* sp.) Cr^{6+} ga javoban EPSning ko'payishi kuzatiladi, ehtimol EPS ning jismoniy to'siq sifatida namoyon bo'lishi va ularning sirtlarining manfiy zaryadi tufayli xelatlanish qobiliyatiga bog'liq bo'lishi mumkin [5]. *Pseudomonas fluorescens* holatida mutatsiyalar (T4 2 shtammi) EPSning "giper ishlab chiqarilishi" ga olib keladi, bu erda polisaxkarid qismi 76% ga etadi va EPS ning amid, karboksil va gidroksil guruhlari Cr^{6+} ning Cr^{3+} ga so'rilishi va qaytarilishida rol o'ynaydi. Ta'kidlash lozimki, kislotali muhitda Cr^{6+} ning yutilish qobiliyati 80 mg/g ga etadi [6].

Ushbu tadqiqotlarning maqsadi Cr^{6+} ionlarining turli konsentratsiyalarida o'stirilgan mikroorganizmlarning ekzopolisaxaridlar hosil qilish faolligini miqdoriy o'rganish hisoblanadi.

Material va metodlar

O'rganish obyektlari: tadqiqot obyekti sifatida Cr^{6+} ionlarining turli yuqori konsentratsiyalariga nisbatan yashovchanligi yuqori bo'lgan Mikrobiologiya instituti kolleksiyasida saqlanayotgan, Samarqand va Qashqadaryo viloyatlari kimyo korxonalarida atrofidagi tuproq naumnalariidan ajratib olingan ajratib olingan *Bacillus licheniformis* 10, *Bacillus cereus* 17, *Bacillus thuringiensis* 94, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* 18 kulturalaridan foydalanildi.

O'stirish sharoitlari: bakterial shtammlar og'ir metallarning turli konsentratsiyalari qo'shilgan suyuq pepton bulyoniga ekildi va pH 7,1 ga o'rnatildi. Og'ir metallar tuzlari (K_2CrO_4) ozuqa muhitiga 112,04 mg/l va 224,08 mg/l konsentratsiyalarda qo'shildi. Nazorat vositasi sifatida metall ionlari qo'shilmagan muhit ishlatildi. Kulturalar 10 kun davomida 30°C da o'stirildi.

Ekzopolisaxaridlarni (EPS) ajratib olish: bakteriyalar ozuqa muhitidan 7 va 10 kunlarda sentrifuga yordamida 6000 aylanish tezligida 30 daqiqa davomida yig'ib olindi. Biomassadan ajratilgan kultural suyuqlik dastlab xloroform+butanol (4:1) aralashmasida 10:1 nisbatda 1 soat davomida inkubatsiya qilindi. So'ngra sentrifuga yordamida oqsilli cho'kma ajratib olindi. Supernatant etanol qo'shib cho'ktirildi (1:1,5) va 4 °C da 24 soat davomida saqlandi. Cho'kmalar sentrifuga yordamida yig'ib olindi va qolgan etanolni bug'lantirish uchun 30-40 °C li quritish shkafiga solindi. Ish so'ngida, cho'kmaning quruq massasi nazoratga nisbatan aniqlandi [7,8].

Olingan natijalar va muhokamasi

Tajriba davomida to'rtta bakteriya shtamlari - *Bacillus licheniformis* 10, *Bacillus cereus* 17, *Bacillus thuringiensis* 94 va *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* 18 – olti valentli xrom (Cr^{6+}) kontsentratsiyalari ta'sirida ekzopolisaxaridlarni (EPS) sintez qilish qobiliyati tahlil etildi. Mikroorganizmlarning EPS sintez qilish faolligi kultivatsiya dinamikasida (7 va 10-kunlarida) metallning 112,04 mg/l va 224,08 mg/l kontsentratsiyalarida aniqlangan. O'stirishning 7-kuni *Bacillus licheniformis* 10 nazoratda 104 mg/l, Cr^{6+} ning 112,04 mg/l va 224,08 mg/l kontsentratsiyalari qo'shilganda esa mos ravishda 177 mg/l va 94 mg/l EPS hosil bo'ldi. Shunday qilib, xromning o'rtacha kontsentratsiyasida EPS sintezi uchun sezilarli stimulyat kuzatildi (+58,7%), bu hujayraning metall stressiga faol himoya reaksiyasini ko'rsatishi mumkin (1-jadval). Nazoratda *Bacillus cereus* 17 - 87 mg/l, Cr^{6+} ning 112,04 mg/l va 224,08 mg/l kontsentratsiyalarida esa 68 mg/l va 63 mg/l EPS hosil qildi. Ushbu ma'lumotlar erta bosqichlarda Cr^{6+} ta'sirida EPS sintezining kamayishini ko'rsatadi. Nazoratda *Bacillus thuringiensis* 94 - 106 mg/l, Cr^{6+} ning 112,04 mg/l va 224,08 mg/l kontsentratsiyalarida — 115 mg/l va 97 mg/l EPS sintezladi, bu esa polisaxaridlar ishlab chiqarishdagi ahamiyatsiz o'zgarishlardan dalolat beradi. *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* 18 shtammida EPS sintezini nazorat (76 mg/l) bilan solishtirganda aniq o'sishini

1-jadval

Bakteriyalar tomonidan Cr^{6+} ionining turli kontsentratsiyalarida hosil bo'lgan EPS miqdori

Mikroorganizmlar	Cr^{6+} ning turli kontsentratsiyalarida EPS miqdori, mg/l					
	7-kun			10-kun		
	Nazorat	112,04 mg/l	224,08 mg/l	Nazorat	112,04 mg/l	224,08 mg/l
<i>Bacillus licheniformis</i> 10	104±6,0	177±5,6	136±6,1	119±9,7	94±3,5	89±5,8
<i>Bacillus cereus</i> 17	87±3,5	68±5,5	63±4,5	87±6,6	120±9,5	80±7,0
<i>Bacillus thuringiensis</i> 94	106±8,3	115±7,6	97±9,6	162±6,1	190±9,5	103±5,8
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i> 18	76±6,5	147±6,0	102±3,5	81±4,5	108±5,2	106±6,0

ko'rsatdi: Cr^{6+} ning 112,04 mg/l kontsentratsiyasida EPS ishlab chiqarishi - 147 mg/l, 224,08 mg/l - 102 mg/l. Ehtimol, bu shtamm metallning yuqori dozalarida ham faol polisaxarid himoyasini amalga oshiradi (1-jadval). Shuni ta'kidlash kerakki, kultivatsiyaning 10-kunida EPS sintezining sezilarli o'sishi ikkita shtammida qayd etilgan: *Bacillus cereus* 17 shtammida Cr^{6+} kontsentratsiyasi 112,04 mg/l bo'lganda, EPS darajasi 120 mg/l (7-kuni - 68 mg/l) tashkil etdi; *Bacillus thuringiensis* 94 ham o'stirishning 10-kunida 190 mg/l gacha (7-kuni 115 mg/l) sezilarli o'sganligini ko'rsatdi, bu esa o'stirishning keyingi bosqichlarida o'zini namoyon qiladigan akumulativ, adaptiv javobni ko'rsatadi. Ushbu ma'lumotlar shuni ko'rsatadiki, ba'zi shtammlar vaqt o'tishi bilan Cr^{6+} ni qarshilik mexanizmlarini faollashtirib, himoya biopolimerlarini to'playdi.

Og'ir metallar, shu jumladan Cr^{6+} ta'sirida mikroorganizmlarda ekzopolisaxaridlarning sintezi biologik moslashuvning asosiy mexanizmlaridan biridir. EPS ko'plab himoya funktsiyalarini bajaradi: hujayra va toksikant o'rtasida to'siq hosil bo'lishidan biopolimerlar yuzasida metall ionlarining xelyatsiyasiga qadar [9]. O'rtacha Cr^{6+} konsentratsiyasining (112,04 mg/L) EPS ishlab chiqarishga ijobiy ta'siri, ayniqsa *B. licheniformis* va *P. aeruginosa* kulturalarida polisaxaridlar almashinuvini faollashtiradigan stressni qo'zg'atish bilan bog'liq bo'lishi mumkin. Shunga o'xshash hodisalar Dog'an va boshqalar (2011) va Yang va boshqalar (2023) asarlarida tasvirlangan [11,12]. Bunda Cr^{6+} ionlari metallotolerant bakteriyalarda EPS giperproduksiyasini qo'zg'atishi mumkinligi ko'rsatilgan. Boshqa tomondan, Cr^{6+} ning yuqori konsentratsiyasida (224,08 mg / L) EPS ishlab chiqarishning kamayishi metallning toksik ta'siri bilan bog'liq bo'lishi mumkin, bu hujayralarning sintetik faolligini buzadi. Xuddi shunday dozaga bog'liq bostiruvchi ta'sir ilgari *Bacillus* va *Pseudomonas* spp uchun ko'rsatilgan [12]. *B. cereus* va *B. thuringiensis* kulturalarida o'stirishning 10-kuni EPS ishlab chiqarishning kuzatilgan o'sishi bu shtammlarning sekinroq moslashishini va uzoq muddatli o'stirishda qarshilik mexanizmlarining rivojlanishini ko'rsatishi mumkin.

Shunday qilib, bizning natijalarimiz Cr(VI) tomonidan qo'zg'atilgan EPS sintezi bioremediatsiya texnologiyalarida qo'llanilishi mumkin bo'lgan muhim mikrobial himoya mexanizmi ekanligini ta'kidlaydi.

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